

VISS

D8.1 – Project Management

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Technical references

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Project Coordinator	José Antonio Plaza Hernández CETEC coordination@viss-project.org
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* PU = Public- Public, fully open, e.g. web (Deliverables flagged as public will be automatically published in CORDIS project's page).

SEN – Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement

Classified R-UE/EU-R – EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Classified C-UE/EU-C – EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Classified S-UE/EU-S – EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444

Document History

v	Date	Beneficiary	Modifications
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v0.2	22/11/2023	KVC	Revised version based on the comments of José Benedicto and Julia Ferrando
v1.0	30/11/2023	CETEC	First final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, submitted to EC.
v2.0	28/08/2025	CETEC	Second final version, approved by the WP leader and the project coordinator, submitted to EC, including updated personnel on the Project Management Board (page 7), corrected references to Section 4 (pages 8, 11, 15), and Section 3.2.1 (page 9) and a clarification on deliverables extension exceptions (page 15).

Verification and approval v1.0

	Name	Date
Verification Final Draft by WP leader	José Antonio Plaza (CETEC)	30/11/2023
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	Name	Date
Verification Final Draft by WP leader	Carmen Fernández (CETEC)	28/08/2025
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Table of contents

- 1. List of abbreviations 5
- 2. Objectives and scope..... 5
- 3. Project Management..... 6
 - 3.1. Governance structure6**
 - 3.1.1. General assembly (GA).....7
 - 3.1.2. Project Management Board (PMB).....7
 - 3.1.3. ViSS Meetings.....8
 - 3.2. Project monitoring9**
 - 3.2.1. ViSS internal monitoring9
 - 3.2.2. ViSS official monitoring12
 - 3.3. Project Deliverables14**
 - 3.3.1. General elaboration rules14
 - 3.3.2. Deliverable quality assurance15
- 4. ViSS online repository 17
- 5. Other relevant information 19
- 6. References 19

List of Tables

- Table 1: General operational procedures for ViSS governance bodies8

List of Figures

- Figure 1: ViSS organisational structure6
- Figure 2: ViSS internal information flow10
- Figure 3: ViSS official information flows12
- Figure 4: ViSS deliverables review15
- Figure 5: ViSS project Online Repository folders17
- Figure 6: ViSS WPs folder content17
- Figure 7: ViSS partner folder content.18
- Figure 8: ViSS official documents & templates folder content.....18
- Figure 9: Meetings, Mailing List and Logos folders content18

1. List of abbreviations

CA	Consortium Agreement
DoA	Description of the Action
GA	General Assembly
IPR	Intellectual Property Right
PC	Project Coordinator
PMB	Project Management Board
PM ²	P-M squared
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design
ViSS	Viable, safe and sustainable PHBV value chain for food packaging applications
WP	Work Package

2. Objectives and scope

The objective of this Deliverable is to establish and describe the methodology, procedures, and activities of planning, organizing, securing, monitoring, and managing the resources and work necessary to deliver the specific Project goals and objectives in an effective and efficient way.

This Project Management Guideline and Quality Plan is based on PM2 methodology, a Project Management Methodology developed by the European Commission, though has been tailored to be applied for ViSS Project, according to the Project's specific needs, and will cover the execution phase of the Project. This deliverable comprises the activities and procedures for ViSS Project Management and Quality Assurance.

ViSS is a forty-eight-months project whose work plan is broken down into eight work-packages, which are also broken down into several tasks, including as well twelve Milestones scheduled during the life cycle of the project, as explained in detail in the project DoA document.

Deliverable 8.1 was submitted on time. **For version 2.0, several changes have been implemented based on EC comments.** These include correcting references to Section 4 throughout the document, renaming Section 3.2.1 to "ViSS internal monitoring," and adding a clarification on exceptions related to deliverable extensions. Additionally, the personnel on the Project Management Board have been updated, and various typos and formatting errors have been corrected.

3. Project Management

This section describes the project management elements, structure and procedures that aim at ensuring the successful completion of the Project's objectives. This chapter defines in detail the governance structure, establishes the contact details of the key consortium staff, and describes the model for monitoring the Project by setting up auto-control mechanisms. The chapter also describes the documentation processes in terms of templates, flow of information and structure of the Deliverables.

3.1. Governance structure

The consortium organizational and management structure was decided during the planning phase of the Project and is described in detail in the CA, according to different bodies and management positions and responsibilities.

This organizational structure is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: ViSS organisational structure

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The ViSS governance structure includes the following bodies of the project:

- The General Assembly (GA).
- Project Management Board (PMB).

The coordination and management activities of the project (WP8) are performed by the Project Coordinator, which is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the partners of the project and the Funding Authority, in cooperation with two interacting bodies GA and PMB.

The work is organized into Work Packages, led by Work Package Leaders, who coordinate, plan, monitor and report to the Project Management Board about WP progress at least every month, during fixed time slot conference calls.

More details and information are described in the ViSS CA.

3.1.1. General assembly (GA)

The General Assembly is the ultimate decision-making body of the Consortium and shall consist of one representative of each partner. The Coordinator shall chair all meetings.

The GA has decision-making power with respect to non-operational, strategic, and long-term issues, however it shall be free to act on its own initiative to formulate proposals and take decisions in accordance with the procedures set out in the CA. In addition, all proposals made by the Project Management Board shall also be considered and decided upon by the General Assembly.

The following decisions shall be taken by the General Assembly:

- Content, finances, and intellectual property rights
- Evolution of the consortium
- Appointment of the Project Management Board.

3.1.2. Project Management Board (PMB)

Project Management Board as the supervisory body for the execution of the Project which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly.

The Project Management Board shall consist of the Project Coordinator, Technical Manager, SSbD Manager, Outreach Manager and the Work Packages Leaders.

According to the first DoA version, the PMB is composed by the following positions of responsibility:

- Project Coordinator (CETEC). Project Coordination Team: Carmen Fernández, Juan Agüera, Ana Crespo.
- Technical Manager (CETBIO). In charge of WP1-WP5. María Nicolás.
- SSbD Manager (KVC). In charge of WP6. José Benedicto.
- Outreach Manager (ICONS); In charge of WP7. Chiara Locuratolo.
- Work Packages Leaders
 - CETEC-WP1; Cristina Muro.
 - CETBIO-WP2; María Nicolás.

- HP-WP3; Nydia Badillo.
- CETBIO-WP4; María Nicolás.
- PROPA-WP5; Davide Crapanzano.
- KVC-WP6; José Benedicto.
- ICONS-WP7; Chiara Locuratolo.
- CETEC-WP8; Carmen Fernández.

The Project Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the Project Management Board.

In ViSS project the Project Coordinator is a figure of management composed of a team that develops their responsibility according to this distribution of the work:

- Primary Project coordinator. Carmen Fernández (CETEC). General responsible of the ViSS project coordination.
- Secondary Project coordinator and Financial Project Coordinator. Juan Agüera (CETEC). Involved in the coordination of WP6, WP7 and WP8, and in charge of the administrative and financial coordination.
- Secondary Project Coordinator. Ana Crespo (CETEC). Involved in the coordination of WP7.

Contact details of all ViSS partners are available on the ViSS Online Repository (see section 4 of this document).

3.1.3. ViSS Meetings

This section details the main operating procedures of the two ViSS governance bodies. All detailed rules and procedures are included in the CA approved by all members of the consortium.

Table 1: General operational procedures for ViSS governance bodies

	General assembly	Project management Board
Ordinary meeting	At least twice a year	At least quarterly
Extraordinary meeting	At any time upon written request of the Project Management Board or 1/3 of the Members of the General Assembly	At any time upon written request of any Member of the Project Management Board
Participants	One representative person (at least) from each partner	One representative person (at least) from each member
Notice of a meeting	45 calendar days for an ordinary meeting, and 15 days for an extraordinary meeting	15 calendar days for an ordinary meeting, and 7 days for an extraordinary meeting
Sending the agenda	21 calendar days for an ordinary meeting, and 10 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting	7 calendar days for both

Adding agenda items	14 calendar days for an ordinary meeting, and 7 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting	2 calendar days for both
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Concerning voting rules, each Governance Body shall not deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds (2/3) of its members are present or represented (quorum).

If the quorum is not reached, the chairperson shall convene another ordinary meeting within 15 calendar days. If the quorum is not reached in this meeting, the chairperson shall convene an extraordinary meeting which shall be entitled to decide by majority even if less than the quorum of Members is present or represented.

Each Member of a Consortium Body present or represented in the meeting shall have one vote.

3.2. Project monitoring

The Project Coordinator team is the ultimate body for the right monitoring and control of the project. To do this a Cyclical Quality Assurance scheme (Planning—Realization—Analysis—Revision) will be used.

This cyclical approach will enable the consortium, specially the PMB, to monitor costs, time and quality of ViSS Project.

- Costs means that tasks are completed within the budget assigned in the Gant Agreement.
- Time means that Milestones, Deliverables and official reports are available on time.
- Quality means that the results reach the Project objectives.

3.2.1. ViSS internal monitoring

3.2.1.1. ViSS internal information flows

This section describes the bottom-up and top-down communication flows in ViSS Project. The ViSS internal bottom-up information flow facilitates the project's progress by continuously exchanging information with the Project Consortium and supporting the completion of assigned work. To do this it will be performed at three different levels:

- Information at task level by the Task leader.
- Information at WP level by the WP leader.
- Information at Project level by the Project Management Board.

The main tools for the ViSS project monitoring are the deliverables. The information necessary to complete these deliverables and the rest of the information required by the European Commission will be compiled following the process, templates and times described in the following Figure 2.

Figure 2: ViSS internal information flow

In ViSS each WP leader is responsible for the WP and its tasks, including a sufficient effort/calendar control; and coordination, both internally and with other WPs, as well as the planning and periodicity of the WPs-reports (from the partners to the Task leader using the Partner activities template; and, from the Task leader to the WP leader using the task status report).

WP leaders, based on the information collected through the Task status reports as described above, will prepare a WP progress report (using the template called WP status report) that they will send monthly to the corresponding ViSS manager, specifically:

- Technical Manager. In charge of WP1, WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP5. María Nicolás (CETBIO).
- SSbD Manager. In charge of WP6. José Benedicto (KVC).
- Outreach Manager. In charge of WP7. Chiara Locuratolo (ICONS).

Once the WP status report has been reviewed by the ViSS manager, they will send it to the Project Coordination Team (monthly).

In a complementary way, all ViSS partners are responsible to communicate the potential issues and/or changes that detect. To do this, they must inform the corresponding ViSS Manager when the issue/change is detected and also include this information in their periodic report through the Partner activities template.

On the other hand, as show in the figure 2, the WP leaders two months before to the Periodic Report (moths 16, 34 and 46) will elaborate a summary report of the activities developed in their WP, using the template named WP summary report. This report will be revised by the corresponding ViSS manager and will send to the Project Coordination responsible (at least 1.5 months before the periodic report date).

Furthermore, all the ViSS meeting decisions, agreements, or discussions will be registered through minutes (minutes meeting template). These minutes will be uploaded on the ViSS platform once it

will be accepted by all participants. To do it, the chairperson (Task leader, WP leader, ViSS Manager, or Project Coordinator Team) will elaborate and send a draft to all participants. The minutes shall be considered accepted if, within 15 calendar days from sending, no participant has sent an objection in writing to the chairperson with respect to the accuracy of the draft of the minutes.

More information about ViSS templates in section 4.

Regarding the ViSS internal top-down information flow will be deployed by direct communication through the Project Coordinator Team. To do this conventional communication channels could be used as email (coordination@viss-project.org), telephone (CETEC's phone +34 968632200), or in person in the ViSS meetings.

3.2.1.2. ViSS process for implementing corrective actions

The process for implementing corrective actions is based on the ViSS internal information process (described in section 5.2.1.1 of this document), and the official reporting processes (continuous reporting and periodic reporting).

In this document corrective action is an action aimed at removing the cause of product issues or unwanted deviations in order to prevent their future recurrence.

- When a ViSS Partner detects an issue, deviation and/or change, this will be communicated in accordance with the process described in section 5.2.1.1. After receiving the information, the ViSS Manager (corresponding to the affected WP) will be able to:
- If the issue or deviation is operational and only affects one WP. The ViSS manager will inform the WP leader who, after analyzing the deviation or issue, will apply the corrective action(s) necessary to solve it. The entire process will be recorded in the corresponding monthly report (WP status report) of the WP.
- If the issue or deviation is operational and affects more than one WP. The ViSS manager together with the leaders of the affected WPs will agree and adopt the appropriate actions to solve the issue or deviation in a consensual manner. The entire process will be recorded in the corresponding monthly report (WP status report) of the WP (s).
- If the issue or deviation is strategic. The ViSS manager will inform the Project coordinator team of the event and the WP leader(s) involved, and a corrective plan will be jointly developed. If, in the opinion of the Project Coordinator, the issue or deviation is significant, an Extraordinary PMB Meeting will be convened; otherwise, it will be evaluated at the scheduled ordinary meetings.

The PMB, after evaluating the issue or deviation, is the one who decides whether or not to involve the GA.

In this document, an operational issue or deviation is understood to be one that does not modify the objective of the Task or Work Package and also has no effect on compliance with the ViSS monitoring variables (quality, time and cost). In this sense strategic issue or deviation is that are not operational.

3.2.2. ViSS official monitoring

In Horizon Europe projects there's two types of reporting:

- Continuous Reporting: available from the beginning of a project.
- Periodic Reporting: available at the end of a reporting period.

Figure 3: ViSS official information flows

3.2.2.1. ViSS Continuous Reporting

The continuous reporting is available from the beginning of the project (1st of September 2023) in the Grant Management services in the Funding & Tenders Portal (<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/home>).

The contents that must be included in this module are (for informational purposes only):

- **Project Summary** including information about context and overall objectives, work performed and main achievements, Results beyond the state of the art, and Policy relevant evidence of your project
- **Researches Involved in the Project.** Data (information on the researcher) originally included in the Grant Agreement are available for editing via the Continuous Reporting.
- **Deliverables.** Online repository for uploading the Project Deliverables.
- **Milestones.** Online tool to report on the achievement of Milestones.
- **Critical Risks.** Critical implementation risks and mitigation actions for foreseen risks and unforeseen risks.
- **Publications.** Online tool to cover the publications linked to the Project including suggested publications from OpenAIRE (a list of publications retrieved directly from OpenAire and linked to the Project) and Project Publications (publications linked to the Project and that have been imported by the Consortium).
- **Results.** A results questionnaire including information about results and results ownership.
- **Dissemination Activities.** Dissemination questionnaire that concerns the public disclosure of the Project results via dissemination activities by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including the scientific publications in

any medium.

- **Communications Activities.** Communications Activities questionnaire lists all communication activities for the Project.
- **Standards.** Standards questionnaire including information about: Definition of standardization activities; Description of a given standardization activities and reference to the relevant group; Types of standardization bodies involved; Names of standardization bodies involved; Reference to an existing Standard (if available).
- **Intellectual Property Rights (IPR).** Online tool to inform about IPR of the Project (add IPR, editing IPR and deleting IPR)
- **Datasets.** Datasets questionnaire for informing about Open Science requirements including Datasets suggested by OpenAIRE (a list of available datasets retrieved directly from OpenAire and linked to the Project. Each record can then be imported to the Project Datasets or discarded); and Project Datasets (shows the datasets linked to the Project and that have been imported by the Consortium).
- **Impact.** Impact questionnaire including information about: Technology readiness; Sustainable Development Goal (SDGs); and Overall Citizen engagement.
- **Impact Continuation.** Impact questionnaire including information about: scientific; societal; environmental; economic impact(s) resulting from the Project's implementation.
- **Other results.** Other Results questionnaire for including a list the Project results other than those included in the Results tab.

The continuous reporting tool is available in a collaborative way (all ViSS partners can edit). However, in order to guarantee the quality of the information, **only the Project Coordination Team of ViSS will complete this information.**

3.2.2.2. ViSS Periodic Reporting

ViSS consortium must officially report the Project's progress together with all eligible costs after each reporting period in its **Periodic Report**. Periods in ViSS are:

- P1: from M1 to M18
- P2: from M19 to M36
- P3: from M37 to M48

Periodic Reports include a technical report and a financial report.

Completing the technical part includes the following (for informational purposes only):

- Part A – The Project Coordination Team will update the tables on an ongoing basis in the continuous reporting module. The information in the tables is then automatically compiled to create part A.
- Part B – Will be prepared outside the grant management tool, using the official template. When done, it will be saved as a single PDF file and uploaded to the (Funding and Tenders portal) grant management system.
- Due to the limited timeframe, a 60 days slot, for preparing both reports (technical and financial), it shall be imperative that all partners provide the Financial Coordinator with a preliminary financial report outlining expected costs for each reporting period no later than 15 days before the periodic report starts.
- The financial report includes a financial statement, an explanation on the use of resources, and a request for payment. Completing the financial statement includes different steps:
- All beneficiaries will fill in their own financial statement, electronically sign it and submit it to the Project Coordinator. No financial statement submitted shall be included in the periodic report without the favourable opinion of the Financial Coordinator to the above-mentioned preliminary financial report.
- Users who can fill in the statement include the Participant Contacts, Project Financial Signatories, Task Managers, but only the Project Financial Signatory (PFSIGN) can electronically sign and submit the statement. For this reason, all partners will make sure they have assigned an FSIGN user to VISS in their organization.

The Project Coordinator may decide to submit the report without financial statement from certain partners (e.g., if a beneficiary cannot submit its individual financial statement on time) therefore those costs would not be considered for that particular interim payment.

3.3. Project Deliverables

The Deliverables are the main tools for both internal monitoring and official monitoring of the ViSS project. Deliverable submission is an obligation for all beneficiaries according to the Grant Agreement. The Project Coordinator is responsible for submitting all deliverables at their due date according to the List of Deliverables (see DoA, Part A, pages 19 to 22).

3.3.1. General elaboration rules

The deliverables will be prepared according to the Deliverable Template (see ViSS Online Repository), in compliance with its format, logos, statements and disclaimers.

In the phase of Deliverable elaboration, the following rules have to be taken into consideration:

- Objectives have to be clear from the beginning.
- The document has to be concise: giving a lot of information clearly and in a few words; expressing what needs to be said without unnecessary words; avoiding useless lengthening.
- Synthesize, summarize and get to the point always.

- To avoid repeating contents already described in previous Deliverables or in the Grant Agreement (always use references for that).
- Any bibliographic citation has to be referenced, using a numeric type of citation such as IEEE.

Deliverables should generally not exceed a 30-page limit. Exceptions may be made for documents covering complex scientific or technical topics that require additional length. To maintain clarity while still providing comprehensive information, all supplementary material, such as extensive data sets, detailed charts, or additional figures, should be included in **annexes**.

3.3.2. Deliverable quality assurance

In order to ensure the availability on time and the quality of the ViSS deliverables, a specific process for checking its quality has been established. This process is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: ViSS deliverables review

To implement this process, a Plan to review Deliverables has been elaborated including for each Deliverable described in the DoA:

- Deliverable responsible: partner, person in charge, and contact data (email and telephone number).
- Deliverable reviewer: reviewer partner, person in charge, and contact data (email and telephone number).
- Timelines: 1st Due Date (Responsible send to the Reviewer), 2nd Due Date (Reviewer send back to the Responsible), 3th Due Date (Responsible send to the ViSS Manager), 4th Due Date (ViSS Manager send to Coordination Team), and Final Due Date (Coordination Team send to the European Commission).

This Plan is available in the ViSS Online Repository (see section 4 of this document).

The outcome of the review process will not be reflected in any formal document for avoiding any more bureaucratic burdens, but the partners involved in the process will take into account the following two criteria:

Scientific criteria:

- **Relevance:** How relevant for the Project are the topics included, and more specifically for the WP producing the Deliverable? This question refers to relevance of contents according to the Project objectives and the WP's specific objectives.
- **Completeness:** Have all the topics of the Deliverable been properly covered? This question refers not only to the scope of the Deliverable but also to relevant aspects according to the scientific and technical requirements from other WPs in ViSS that are susceptible to be affected by the contents of this Deliverable.
- **Appropriate level of detail:** Is there an appropriate level of detail in the analysis of each element? This question refers to providing sufficient information so that all statements, claims, descriptions and conclusions are either self-evident or adequately and scientifically articulated. All information should have the depth needed for the purpose of the document.
- **Innovation:** To what extent the relevant contributions of the Deliverable can be considered novel and innovative? Does the Deliverable point out differences from related state-of-the-art issues? This question refers to the way that new problems or new approaches have been set up by the Deliverable – of course it cannot be applied to all Deliverables in ViSS.
- **Soundness:** How well supported are the conclusions drawn? All pieces of information, statements, claims, descriptions and conclusions should be strongly substantiated, and should be verified or traced to the appropriate sources of reference.
- **Consistency:** Is the information included consistent with regards to other accepted statements, claims, descriptions and conclusions made elsewhere in ViSS or, more generally, in the wider scientific and technical community?
- **References:** Are the references adequate and necessary? This question refers to the appropriateness of the references used to concern the particular scope of the Deliverable.

Format criteria:

- **Readability:** Comfortable and easy-reading, good use of vocabulary, grammar and orthography.
- **Terminology:** All specific terms are adequately explained, in order to provide an appropriate frame of reference for the reader; a glossary might be included.
- **Structure:** Which should be coherent and clearly organize different items and issues, while grouping together any appropriate elements.
- **Appearance:** Formatting and physical distribution of images, tables and margins should be appealing and look professional. All Deliverables will be generated according to the common template that is included in the Project collaborative space and which has been used to write this Deliverable as well.

4. ViSS online repository

ViSS Online Repository (or ViSS platform) is an internal, password-restricted web-based shared working environment, a Google Workspace platform created for CETEC as Project Coordinator for the ViSS Project communication and information storage.

Only people assigned by ViSS partners and registered by the Project Coordinator can access the ViSS platform. When a partner needs to update (register or unregister) people on the platform, they must contact the Project Management Team who will guide them until access is complete. For this you can use the email coordination

The following figures 5, 6, 7 & 8, present the structure and contents of the ViSS platform.

Name	Owner	Last modified	File size
ViSS WPs	me	18 Jul 2023	—
ViSS partners	me	18 Jul 2023	—
ViSS official documents & templates	me	18 Jul 2023	—
Meetings	me	12 Jul 2023	—
Mailing lists	me	27 Jul 2023	—
Logos	me	29 Jun 2023	—

Figure 5: ViSS project Online Repository folders

Figure 6: ViSS WPs folder content

Figure 7: ViSS partner folder content.

Figure 8: ViSS official documents & templates folder content.

Figure 9: Meetings, Mailing List and Logos folders content

At the time of approval of this Deliberative all information presented in the ViSS Platform images is

available to ViSS partners as described in this section.

5. Other relevant information

English is the official language in ViSS. All documents must be written in English. Nevertheless, there can be exceptions with some dissemination materials, such as press releases or even technical publications of national reach, which can – if needed – be translated to other languages.

6. References

The following documents have been necessary to develop the ViSS Project Management Guideline and Quality Plan:

- ViSS DoA, which is Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement NUMBER 101081931, and contains the details of how the action (project) will be carried out. This document was prepared during the initiating and planning phase of the project.
- ViSS Grant Agreement Number 101081931.
- ViSS Consortium agreement.
- PM² Project Management Methodology Guide 3.0.1, March 2021.
- PM² Glossary based on the PM² Guide v3.0